

NON-ISOTHERMAL CONSOLIDATION MODELLING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY PREDICTION FOR GLASS/POLYPROPYLENE COMMINGLED FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

A balanced twill weave commingled fabric was consolidated by vacuum forming. Samples were tested in three point bending, and the void content was measured to validate a consolidation model that predicts void content as a function of pressure, time at pressure and temperature. Additionally, voids located in the inter-tow region are also considered. A simple heat transfer model is introduced in the existing isothermal consolidation model to account for the effect of temperature on the consolidation. A microscope image analysis technique was used to investigate the evolution of the microstructure during consolidation and to quantify levels of void content. These measurements were correlated with the mechanical properties of laminates consolidated and two simple stress fracture criteria are used to predict the strength of laminate composites containing voids.

KEYWORDS: commingled, void content, mechanical properties, consolidation model

INTRODUCTION

Textile composite materials are of increasing interest not only in the automotive and aerospace industries, but also in other fields such as in sport and the marine sectors. However, textile composite materials are not always easy to form and consolidate, and defects such as voids, fibre displacements or wrinkling can inhibit the mechanical performance of the final component.

This paper presents an extension to the previously published isothermal consolidation model [1], where an extensive review of consolidation models was presented. Here, a heat transfer model is introduced to predict the material temperature profile during a non-isothermal vacuum forming process. This profile is used to calculate the viscosity of the resin at each time step during the process. Previous research showed that during the first two minutes of isothermal consolidation voids were also located in the inter-tow region. Hence, inter-tow void content is also accounted for. Excellent correlation between measured and predicted void content is observed.

It is difficult to predict the effect that voids have on the strength of composite laminates because of their irregular shape and distribution. However, the shape of the curve of strength versus void content may be explained using simple stress fracture criteria. Two criteria - the point stress and the average stress criteria - predict the strength of laminates containing discontinuities. Both criteria assume that fracture occurs when the strength at some characteristic distance away from the discontinuity reaches the stress of a fully consolidated laminate. Good agreement between measured and predicted mechanical properties is observed.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Materials

The material used for these experiments was a balanced 2x2 twill weave fabric of bulk density 1.5 g/cm³ consisting of a yarn of 60% by mass commingled E-glass and polypropylene supplied by Saint-Gobain Vetrotex under the registered trade mark Twintex®. The glass fibre radius is $r_f = 9.25 \mu\text{m}$. The thickness of a fully consolidated layer is approximately 0.5 mm and the corresponding fibre volume fraction is 0.35. The number of reinforcement fibres per yarn is $N_f=1600$ (as stated by the manufacturer).

Specimen Manufacture

An isothermal vacuum forming process was initially adopted in order to simplify the modelling procedure, so that consolidation could be considered to occur at constant temperature [1]. This process differed from that used typically in industry, where the vacuum is applied during the heating cycle. In the present paper, results from non-isothermal consolidation of glass/PP commingled fabrics are also presented.

Three layers of fabric were placed over a single aluminium flat plate (150 mm x 250 mm), and sealed in a vacuum bag. This arrangement was placed in a hot air oven, preheated to 215°C, and pressure applied until the material reached 180°C. Finally, the laminate (still sealed within the vacuum bag) was quenched in a cold water bath until the temperature was below 120°C. Applied pressure was varied between 60 mbar and 950 mbar in order to obtain samples a range of void contents. Thickness ranged from 1.55 to 1.80 mm due to the variable void content of specimens.

Void content analysis

To understand the influence of processing parameters on the microstructure and hence the mechanical properties of laminates, a large number of photomicrographs were taken from each plaque using a microscope fitted with a digital camera. Using an image analysis technique the range of grey levels characteristic of the voids was used to measure the percentage of the image corresponding to voids [2].

CONSOLIDATION MODELLING

A consolidation model that predicted void content during an isothermal vacuum forming process has been presented and validated in previous paper [1]. This consolidation model was based on the analysis of micrographs taken at different stages of the consolidation and assumed impregnation to be the main consolidation mechanism. However, an industrial vacuum consolidation process for commingled materials is non-isothermal, since the pressure is applied as the material is heated. Therefore, the next stage in the development of the model is to incorporate a heat transfer sub-model, allowing temperature and therefore viscosity to be calculated at each time step.

In the following sections, a model for non-isothermal consolidation of commingled thermoplastic composites is presented. These is based in the following assumptions:

- The matrix is a non-Newtonian fluid.
- Pressure is uniform and remains constant during forming.
- The width and length of the fabric are much larger than the thickness so that matrix pressure is constant in the cross section.
- The consolidation of the whole laminate can be described by the consolidation behaviour of a single representative yarn.

- A yarn is constituted of dry fibre bundles surrounded by the matrix pool. The flow front is considered to advance radially.
- Flow takes place in the direction orthogonal to the fibres.
- Due to the low pressure applied (vacuum pressure), capillary flow must be considered in the impregnation model.
- No void nucleation, migration or dissolution in the matrix is assumed to occur.

Four sub-models are used: a permeability sub-model, a compaction sub-model, a heat transfer sub-model and an impregnation sub-model.

Permeability sub-model

The permeability sub-model determines the property of the fibre bundle that characterises the ease of fluid impregnation. Here, the modified Kozeny-Carman equation is used to predict the transverse fibre bundle permeability [3].

$$K = \frac{r_f^2}{4k'} \frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{v_a}{v_f}} - I \right)^3}{\frac{v_a}{v_f} + I} \quad (1)$$

The value of v_a , fibre volume fraction at zero permeability, was calculated to be 0.91 assuming hexagonal close packing of fibres. Due to the lack of data available to represent the permeability behaviour of the material used in these experiments, the empirical constant k' is 50 as determined from the isothermal consolidation model [1].

Compaction sub-model

To evaluate the compaction behaviour at pressures of up to 1 bar compaction tests were performed on the reinforcement after the matrix had been removed by burn-off. Four samples composed by three layers of reinforcement each were lubricated with 10ml of Elfolna 15 (mineral oil supplied by Elf). The measured behaviour of the fibre bed can be represented by a power law relationship:

$$P_f = 190V_f^{7.46} \quad (2)$$

The fibre volume fraction in a yarn v_f differs from the overall fibre volume fraction V_f . Thus, v_f can be calculated using a modified value of the fibre volume fraction of the laminate. Considering that the tow shape is defined by an elliptical equation of order n (Eqn. 3). The initial value of n that equals the area of the initial tow cross-section was estimated to be 0.1.

$$\frac{y}{b/2} = \left(1 - \left(\frac{x}{a/2} \right)^2 \right)^n \quad 0 \leq n \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

where a is the with of a yarn ($a=5mm$) and b is the thickness of a yarn, which can be calculated as a function of the number of layers n_l and the current thickness of the laminate h using, Eqn. 4.

$$b = \frac{h}{2n_l} \quad (4)$$

It is observed from experiments that the void content is a function of the total thickness of the laminate. In fact, the void content can be calculated as:

$$V_c = \frac{h - h_\infty}{h} \quad (5)$$

The current thickness can be obtained from Eqn. 3, hence the current fibre volume fraction can be calculated as:

$$V_f = V_{f\infty} \frac{h_\infty}{h} \quad (6)$$

where $V_{f\infty}$ is the fibre volume fraction of a fully consolidated laminate ($V_{f\infty}=0.35$ for Twintex®).

Using simple geometric relationships, the fibre volume fraction within a yarn can be calculated using Eqn. 7, where the area of the tow cross-section (A_{Tow}) has to be calculated numerically as a function of the exponent n .

$$v_f = \frac{V_f ab}{A_{Tow}} \quad (7)$$

Heat transfer sub-model

The consolidation of flat laminates by non-isothermal vacuum forming can be solved thermodynamically by considering a composite plane wall consisting of two parallel layers [4]: the composite laminate and the tool. Let k_1 and k_2 be thermal conductivities, and α_1 and α_2 the thermal diffusivities for the aluminium tool and laminate layers, respectively.

The assumptions made in deriving the mathematical formulation of the unidirectional time dependent heat conduction problem are:

- There is no energy generation within the composite.
- The thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity are temperature independent and uniform within each layer.
- The two layer arrangement is sufficiently long and wide in comparison to the thickness.
- A constant temperature is maintained inside the oven.

The heat conduction problem can be now represented by:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{\alpha_i} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

where ξ is the temperature difference between two points across the thickness and α is the thermal diffusivity ($k/\rho c$), where k is the thermal conductivity, ρ is the density and c is the heat capacity. The unconsolidated laminate consists of glass fibres, pools of polypropylene and air. The exact thermal properties of the laminate will be dependant on the temperature, fibre volume fraction and arrangement of the constituents. The presence of voids in the laminate decreases both the thermal conductivity and the material average density. Consequently, the thermal diffusivity is also altered.

The bulk properties of the laminate will change as compactions occurs, air is extracted from the laminate and compressed as voids are reduced, and as the temperature of the laminate changes during processing. However, the simulation was carried out assuming that temperature parameters are time

and temperature independent. As Tavman et al. [5] demonstrated, it may be assumed that the laminate behaves as a rule of mixtures material. In this case, the laminate thermal properties are combined serially, to give the through thickness laminate properties.

The laminate thermal conductivity can be calculated as

$$k_l = \frac{1}{\frac{v_{fglass}}{k_{glass}} + \frac{v_{fPP}}{k_{PP}} + \frac{v_{fair}}{k_{air}}} \quad (9)$$

and the product ρc

$$\rho_l c_l = v_{fglass} \rho_{glass} c_{glass} + v_{fPP} \rho_{PP} c_{PP} + v_{fair} \rho_{air} c_{air} \quad (10)$$

Table 1 Constants values for heat transfer model

Material	k (W/mK)	ρ (kg/m ³)	c (J/kgK)
Glass	1	2550	840
Polypropylene	0.288	900	1090
Air	0.034	0.783	1021

The constants used in these simulations are shown in Table 1. Solving Eqn. 8 using finite difference analysis, Figure 1 shows a comparison between the measured and the predicted material temperature in the middle of 3 layers of Twintex® during a non-isothermal vacuum forming process. Excellent agreement is observed between measured and predicted material temperature.

Figure 1 Predicted and measured laminate temperature for 3 layers of Twintex® consolidated by non-isothermal vacuum forming.

Impregnation sub-model

Similarly to Bernet et al. [6], Darcy's law is used here to calculate the time increment Δt necessary for the resin to advance a distance $\Delta r_i = R_i - r_i$, where R_i and r_i are the positions of the resin flow front before and after Δt .

$$\Delta t = \frac{(1-v_f)\mu}{K(P_a + P_c - P_g - P_f)} \left[\frac{r_i^2}{2} \ln\left(\frac{r_i}{r_0}\right) - \frac{R_i^2}{2} \ln\left(\frac{R_i}{r_0}\right) - \frac{r_i^2}{4} + \frac{R_i^2}{4} \right] \quad (11)$$

where μ is the non-Newtonian resin viscosity, v_f is the tow fibre volume fraction, r_0 is the initial agglomeration radius, K is the permeability, P_a is the applied pressure, P_c is the capillary pressure and P_g is the internal void pressure (for a vacuum pressure process, P_g is assumed to be zero).

P_c is the capillary pressure, defined here as positive when it enhances resin flow. The capillary pressure can be estimated theoretically using the Young-Laplace equation:

$$P_c = \frac{4\gamma_{lv} \cos \omega}{d_f} \frac{v_f}{1-v_f} \quad (12)$$

where γ_{lv} is the surface tension of the polypropylene and ω is the contact angle between the solid and the liquid. Capillary pressure can be estimated using $\gamma_{lv} = 0.029 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ and $\omega = 89^\circ$. Typical values of capillary pressure are between 50 Pa and 100 Pa for fibre volume fractions between 0.3 and 0.35 respectively. Given that the applied pressure here was 95,000 Pa, capillary pressure should have a negligible effect in this case.

The ideal gas law under general conditions expresses the void pressure. In the case of vacuum forming it is assumed that the ambient pressure is the vacuum, hence P_g equals zero. Otherwise:

$$P_g = P_{am} \frac{r_0^2}{r_i} \left(\frac{1-v_{f0}}{1-v_f} \right) \quad (13)$$

Polypropylene viscosity data obtained at the University of Cambridge was used to fit the Carreau-Yasuda model, Eqn. 14, which is updated at each time step to account for the effect of temperature on viscosity.

$$\mu = a_T \mu_0 \left\{ 1 + (\lambda_{cy} a_T \dot{\gamma})^p \right\}^{(m-1)/p} \quad (14)$$

Here, μ is the viscosity, μ_0 is the zero shear rate viscosity a_T is the shift factor and m, p and λ_{cy} are additional fitting parameters [1]. For high shear rates, when polypropylene shows a shear thinning behaviour, it is observed experimentally that the shear strain rate can be estimated as:

$$\dot{\gamma}_a = \frac{2m+1}{m} \left(\frac{2V}{x} \right) \quad (15)$$

Where x is the fibre spacing and V is the flow velocity, which can be determined from the flow front radius r_i , the flow front radius at the previous time step R_i , and the duration of the time step Δt .

Based on experimental observations it can be stated that small fibre bundles tend to gather within the yarns. Each of these groups is known as an agglomeration, and surrounds a single intra-tow void. Assuming that the commingled yarn contains N_a agglomerations with an initial radius r_0 , the total void content of the yarn at a given time step is given by:

$$V_c = \frac{\pi N_a r_i^2 (1 - v_f)}{A_{Tow}} \quad (16)$$

where

$$A_{Tow} = \frac{N_i \pi r_f^2}{v_{f\infty}} + \pi N_a r_i^2 (1 - v_f) \quad (17)$$

where N_i is the total number of reinforcing fibres in the total commingled yarn and r_f is the fibre radius. In this study the number of fibres in a yarn is $N_i=1600$ and the average initial agglomeration radius was measured at $75\mu\text{m}$ from image analysis.

Micrographs presented in previous paper [1] showed that inter-tow voids disappeared particularly during the first two minutes of consolidation. Therefore, the consolidation model should consider two different problems: the evolution of inter-tow voids and the encroachment of the matrix into fibre bundles to eliminate intra-tow voids. A simple geometric model can represent inter-tow void reduction. This model is based in the assumption that voids are eliminated due to a change in tow shape. The inter-tow void content could be the result of a change in the tow shape - i.e. n in Eqn. 3 is not a constant. Hence, the inter-tow void content can be calculated as:

$$V_{C \text{ Inter-tow}} = \frac{ab - A_{Tow}}{ab} \quad (18)$$

Figure 2 Predicted and measured void content for different levels of pressure.

By introducing the predicted temperature profile in the model, the remaining void content in a non-isothermal vacuum forming process can be calculated. An explanation of how the different sub-models are implemented in a spreadsheet at each time step is presented below.

Firstly, several parameters provided by the manufacturer are required in addition to the boundary conditions. Then, fibre volume fraction and area of the tow are calculated to obtain fibre volume fraction within the yarn and void content in the inter-tow region. The calculated material temperature is then used to obtain the viscosity of the resin, and pressures are calculated. When a vacuum is not

applied, pressure inside the voids could lead to the equilibrium of pressures, consequently stopping the advance of the flow front. In the present case, the pressure inside the voids is assumed negligible. Finally, the time step is calculated using Eqn. 11.

Figure 2 shows the predicted values for void content when the non-isothermal case was analysed. Fitting parameters k' and N_a were 50 and 12 respectively as used in the isothermal model [1]. Predictions showed that inter-tow void content contributed 4.74% to the final void content of a laminate consolidated under 100 mbar. However, no contribution was observed for laminates consolidated at pressures of over 300 mbar. Excellent agreement between the measured and the predicted void content is observed.

EFFECT OF VOID CONTENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Previous work on the isothermal consolidation of glass/PP commingled fabrics showed the effect of void content on flexural strength. Figure 3 shows that void content of over 10% reduced flexural strength by approximately 50%. Figure 4 shows the effect of void content on tensile strength for flat plaques consolidated by a non-isothermal vacuum forming process. Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval.

Whitney et al. [7] presented two related criteria based on stress concentration for predicting the tensile strength of laminated composites containing through thickness discontinuities of general shape. The criteria resulted in a two-parameter model that is capable of predicting strength without resorting to classical concepts from linear elastic fracture mechanics. The two parameters are the strength of a fully consolidated laminate and a characteristic dimension. The first approach assumed that the failure occurs when the stress at some distance away from the void is greater than the strength of a fully consolidated laminate. It is also assumed that the characteristic distance, ψ_1 , is independent of laminate geometry and stress distribution. Assuming circular voids, the consolidation model is able to predict the void radius (r) for each level of void content assuming that the number of agglomerations in a yarn is 12. With these assumptions, the stress failure criteria is

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\infty} = \frac{2}{2 + \zeta_1^2 + 3\zeta_1^4} \quad (19)$$

where σ_∞ is the strength of a fully consolidated laminate (provided by the manufacturer), σ is the predicted laminate strength for a specific void content and

$$\zeta_1 = \frac{r}{r + \psi_1} \quad (20)$$

A second approach was developed by assuming that the failure occurs when the average stress over some distance away from the void is greater than the strength of a fully consolidated laminate. The physical argument for the average stress criterion resides in the assumed ability of the material to redistribute local stress concentrations. As in the point stress criterion the characteristic distance ψ_2 is assumed to be independent of laminate geometry and stress distribution.

$$\zeta_2 = \frac{r}{r + \psi_2} \quad (21)$$

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show comparisons between the experimental and predicted strengths. Values of ψ_1 and ψ_2 equal 25 μm and 60 μm respectively. These values were calculated as an average of the values that minimise the error between predicted and experimental data.

It is difficult to decide which model should be used because reasonable agreement between experimental data and predictions is observed for both criteria. However, the point stress criterion looks marginally better and further work will help to understand the effect of a non-uniform distribution of voids on both models.

Figure 3 Comparison between measured flexural strength, point stress criterion and average stress criterion for different levels of void content on commingled glass/PP consolidated laminates.

Figure 4 Comparison between measured tensile strength, point stress criterion and average stress criterion for different levels of void content on commingled glass/PP consolidated laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental analysis of flat plaques was used to investigate the vacuum forming process for commingled fabrics, woven from yarns of intimately mingled glass and polypropylene fibres. A

model that predicts void content as a function of processing parameters such as pressure, time at pressure and processing temperature was developed.

An existing model based on Darcy's law was modified to account for the effect of shear thinning. A heat transfer model was introduced to predict the material temperature and update the viscosity of the resin, assumed constant over each time step. A compaction model based on experimental data was introduced to predict the deformation of the reinforcement only. Capillary pressure was also accounted for, but this had only a small effect on the predicted void content. Image analysis of micrographs taken at different stages of the consolidation process showed that a large amount of voids were located in the inter-tow region. A simple geometrical model based on the change of the tow shape during consolidation predicted the contribution of the inter-tow voids to the remaining void content. However, in this study inter-tow voids were only observed at consolidation pressures below 300mbar.

The quality of flat plaques manufactured using a simple vacuum forming process was assessed, allowing void content to be measured by an image analysis technique. Measurements from consolidated laminates revealed that a void content of less than 2% could be achieved with suitable process parameters. However, for void levels of over 10%, a reduction in strength of approximately 50% was observed. Simple stress concentration criteria were used to predict the effect of void content on the mechanical properties. This resulted in a two parameter criterion that assumed that the failure occurs when the stress at some distance away from the void is greater than the strength of a fully consolidated laminate. Excellent correlation between measured and predicted strengths was observed.

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